

Cultural disparate English textbooks: An analysis of Bangladesh ELT

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This study investigates locally produced English Language Teaching (ELT) textbooks for higher secondary education in Bangladesh, focusing on the embedded cultural aspects. The research employs content analysis to quantify cultural representation occurrences, revealing a prevalence of Western cultures in the books, while Asian and African cultures are notably underrepresented. The findings expose a cultural bias that portrays women primarily in domestic roles, perceiving their work as mundane. English women, on the other hand, are depicted more gracefully with freedom and peace, despite engaging in conventional activities. Despite some token gestures, such as showcasing women's participation in sports, the study underscores the need for gender-equitable textbooks to challenge learners' conceptual positions and raise awareness of women's rights. The inclusion of international cultures may contribute to a more balanced representation, fostering the development of Bangladeshi learners as global speakers.

Keywords: Cultural Discrimination; ELT Textbook; Negative Portrayal; Target Culture

1. Introduction

Despite the considerable amount of research done on the significance of culture in foreign language teaching (e.g., Canale, 2021; Karakuş, 2021; Risager, 2023), culture remains an unsolved puzzle and a heated discussion in the context of English language teaching around the world. The legitimization of English varieties challenges the teaching of English as a foreign or international language, as fostering only target-culture competence is perhaps no longer possible because the goal of language education is shifting towards global cultural consciousness and intercultural communicative competence. Hence, Weninger and Kiss (2013) called for EFL education with a transformative goal that can only be gained through cultural contemplation and comprehension within the framework of critical pedagogy with materials promoting globally aware language learners—For more on critical pedagogy and emancipation,

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see Salmani Nodoushan and Daftarifard (2011), and Salmani Nodoushan and Pashapour (2016).

An ELT textbook is usually an organized body and the only source of pedagogic information for teachers to teach English in many countries (Graves, 2021). In countries like Bangladesh, it serves as the de facto curriculum determining the content, order, bulk and speed of teaching (Işık, 2018). Thus, it can both aim at conveying information about a particular subject and forming the students' view about their own selves, the society, and the world (Canale, 2016). Therefore, textbooks are used to deliver different types of knowledge, including biased historical facts or subjective truth, in a very convincing way. Consequently, research on textbook analysis has gained increasing attention in the last two decades to investigate cultural and political prejudice.

Recently, researchers (Apple & Christian-Smith, 2017; Canale, 2016) criticized multimodal textbooks on the grounds that they are the outcome of political, economic and cultural struggle, and bargain. National and international writers and all other stakeholders who aim to elucidate a legitimized version of the social world (Gurney & Díaz, 2020) often decide the ideological and discursive complexities in textbook discourse. However, this mechanism is used confirming the comprehensive level of the learners. Therefore, the learners are never in a position to evaluate it. Apparently, they assume that textbook contents are facts rather than institutional opinions, and whatever is written in the textbooks must be believed, adopted, and practiced.

In Bangladesh, integrating cultural learning into the CLT approach is essential for developing intercultural competence and fostering tolerance towards cultural diversity; if ELT materials depict cultural aspects stereotypically, they limit openness and fail to promote linguistics competence and reflective thinking in the Bangladeshi ELT context (Jahan, 2012). Risager (2023) stated that the cultural contents of textbooks are usually not a planned reflection related to the subject matter, but rather of an unreflective/casual and therefore philosophical nature. The textbook writers are linguists, but not a social scientist.

Thus, within the global world, competencies provided by the existing ELT textbooks seemed superficial. Therefore, cultural representations in ELT textbooks necessitate a deep analysis. Hence, this study investigated the cultural representation of *English for Today (Eft)* textbooks produced by NCTB for Classes XI–XII of Bangladesh higher secondary school system. The aim was to highlight the nature and the prevalence of cultural representations dominating the Eft textbooks and assess whether these representations of foreign cultures align with the global status of English as an international language. The research has a significant academic implication for improving

ELT and relevant materials leading to intercultural competence in the context of Bangladesh.

2. Background

In Bangladesh, the purpose of culture learning should be a complement to the CLT process to enhance intercultural competence and grow tolerance for cultural differences. The cultural contents of ELT materials addressing the visible aspects of cultures in a stereotyped manner are restrictive and cannot lead to openness. That is, textbooks do not offer linguistic competence along with reflective thinking through cultural presentations in the Bangladeshi context (Jahan, 2012). Thus, a thorough examination of cultural depictions within ELT textbooks is currently highly relevant.

The depiction of stereotypes in ELT textbooks can potentially intensify cultural prejudices. Studies conducted by Asadullah et al. (2018), Islam and Asadullah (2018), Kabir (2015), and Suchana (2020) in Bangladeshi context reveal how these materials unintentionally perpetuate stereotypes, influencing learners' perceptions and reinforcing discriminatory attitudes. Their research, spanning Bangladesh, Pakistan, Indonesia, and Malaysia, evidenced a bias favoring males but portraying females in traditional, less esteemed roles, and often engaged in domestic activities. The studies underscore a systematic underrepresentation of women, both in textual content and imagery. They even suggest that if aliens were to analyze our school textbooks, they would remain unaware of the significant contributions women make to our society.

Researchers in Asian countries have explored quantitative content analysis (Cortazzi & Jin, 1999; Moran, 2001; Yuen, 2011) as an effective approach to analyzing ELT textbooks (Kim & Paek, 2015; Kusumaningrum et al., 2023; Nurjanah & Umaemah, 2019; Saemee & Nomnian, 2021). Their studies revealed that ELT textbooks are typically grounded in the product, person, practice, and perspective of the target, source, and international cultures. This methodology facilitated the tabulating of cultural occurrences and identification of biases toward specific cultures. Locally produced ELT textbooks in ideal scenarios mirror prevailing cultural norms and values. Nevertheless, ELT materials often may selectively emphasize or diminish specific cultural elements leading to biased representations. Studies by Bose and Gao (2022) and Nurjanah and Umaemah (2019) highlight instances where dominant cultural aspects have overshadowed minority perspectives, contributing to cultural discrimination.

Embedded power dynamics in textbooks can lead to the marginalization of certain cultural groups. Zhang and Chang (2022), for instance, highlighted the overwhelming presence of Western culture in Chinese textbooks,

marginalizing local and international cultures. An array of studies (e.g., Bose & Gao, 2022; Jahan, 2012; Kusumaningrum et al., 2023; Nurjanah & Umaemah, 2019) also found white domination in terms of imperialism and Eurocentrism.

Researchers have frequently lamented the insufficient cultural representations found in ELT materials, which hindered learners' comprehension. Saemee and Nomnian (2021) highlighted how the absence of visual representation led to difficulties in grasping the sociocultural context presented in ELT content. It has been found that the inadequate depiction of various countries impeded learners' readiness for real-world engagements. Kim and Paek (2015) noted a lack of emphasis on intercultural interaction in Korean ELT materials, potentially obstructing multicultural communication.

The presence of cultural prejudice in locally produced ELT textbooks poses challenges for educators. Although many textbooks highlight target culture predominantly, they still lack the necessary intercultural skills to communicate effectively. Thus, researchers such as Asadullah et al. (2018), Kim and Paek (2015), Kusumaningrum et al. (2023) and Suchana (2020) advocate the development of materials that promote cultural and gender equity to enrich the process of learning the English language.

Recently, efforts to address cultural biases in ELT textbooks are gaining momentum. Recent studies (e.g., Kusumaningrum et al., 2023) propose guidelines aimed at developing culturally inclusive materials, emphasizing the significance of authenticity, diversity, and sensitivity. Furthermore, collaborative initiatives involving educators, publishers, and community stakeholders are deemed essential in cultivating culturally equitable ELT resources. Bose and Gao (2022) suggest alternative measures, such as inviting guest speakers from the target or international cultures or integrating online videos into syllabi. Davidson and Liu (2020) recommend incorporating key dimensions of global citizenship, highlighting cultural awareness, tolerance, and social responsibility. Additionally, Kim and Paek (2015) argue that English teachers bear the responsibility of selecting or preparing ELT content that is beneficial for multicultural contexts.

The present study is also in line with the studies reviewed above. It attempted to answer the following research questions:

- 1) What type of cultural discrimination is prevalent in the locally produced ELT textbooks at the HSC level in Bangladesh?
- 2) To what extent has the idea of cultural diversity been addressed in HSC textbooks in Bangladesh?

3. Method

A quantitative content analysis based on Yuen's (2011) categorization of cultural diversity as (1) coding, (2) thinking, (3) communication, and (4) individuals—also labeled as (1) 'products', (2) 'perspectives', (3) 'practices', and (4) 'persons'—was done on the cultural representations of the two (i.e., old and new) textbooks of *English for Today (EfT)* for classes 11 and 12. Content analysis offers an objective, quantified description of how frequently cultural presentations appear in the sampled *EfT* textbooks. As it only counts the frequencies and disregards the contexts, the inferred meaning of the context or the real goal of the research may sometimes be left behind. Hence, a qualitative description would provide the impact of the frequent occurrences and their implied meaning. Thus, this is an interpretive analysis. However, as the prime objective of this study is to record the traces of multicultural elements in teaching ICC, analyzing the two *EfT* textbooks based on content analysis provided a quite rich source of data. The data analysis was done with great care to draw generalized and dependable conclusions from our findings.

3.1. Materials

The sampled textbooks used for this study are old and new textbooks in *English for Today (EfT)* series. In Bangladesh, they are the core English language teaching materials used in classes 1 through 12. The old *EfT* textbook has been developed by the English Language Teaching Improvement Project (ELTIP), mutually subsidized by the Government of Bangladesh and the DFID of the UK Government, in cooperation with the National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB); the NCTB prepared the existing book.

3.2. Procedure

We counted the frequencies of (1) products, (2) perspectives, and (3) practices to provide analytical data for cultural discrimination and (4) persons along with practice for gender discrimination. It was hypothesized that the frequencies of the four cultural elements would help us evaluate (1) which culture is highlighted and which one is marginalized, and (2) whether cultural contents are worthy of teaching intercultural competence.

4. Results

Our major finding indicates that the *EfT* textbooks are predominantly based on Yuen's (2011) model. The textbooks had all the possibilities to equally describe the aspects of target culture, source and international culture; the analyzed textbooks did present all of the cultures. However, it was the target culture that was extensively represented. Evidence shows that the textbooks also contain

some serious gender and cultural discrimination. The detailed findings of the study are presented below.

4.1. Women in domestic chores

The first lesson of the old book starts with a woman carrying a baby beside her husband in an image of a big family. Then gradually, Nazmeen's sister got married, and most of the household chores, including taking care of the grandmother and attending guests, are Nazmeen's responsibility along with her mother. Her aunt gave birth to a baby boy, which made her and her grandmother even busier. Thus, the book initially portrays women as caretakers and doing household chores as mothers, grandmothers, daughters, and wives. It also gives the impression that men, being family members, do not do or help with household chores. On the other hand, Zinnia, in a nuclear family, has her own room and a lot of time to herself. As her working parents and university-going brother do not have time to spend with her, she is always lonely. The book seems to portray that even if Asian women are given a bit of luxury, they remain unhappy. Ultimately, their true happiness lies in being with and taking care of their families.

It was observed in the analyzed books that, in Afghanistan, women are prohibited from doing jobs outside home. They are still expected to remain busy with household activities. The Taj Mahal, built for Shah Jahan's wife, Mumtaz, also seems to support the idea that women in Asia are appreciated as wives and mothers.

In lesson 2, a woman in an apron in the kitchen is about to clean the floor covered with broken plates, probably done by the kids standing in front of the woman. In lesson 3, three hands are shown making oral saline. Three of them are wearing bangles. However, in lesson 4, a professional dignified chef is a man wearing a chef coat and hat in an image. In lesson 'Women Have Rights Too', three types of female abuses are stated in text along with images:

- (1) If she does not give birth to a son this time, the husband will remarry;
- (2) Once a daughter is married off, she can only study if her in-laws wish;
and
- (3) If the father of a wife does not pay dowry as promised, the wife will be sent back to her father's house.

A passage in this lesson states how their husbands maltreat women in Asian culture and how ignorant they are about seeking justice. Hence, the government has introduced the Women and Children's Repression Act to protect their rights.

In the lesson on 'Food Trends' in the new book, a dialogue between Purnima and her mother shows a stereotyped conversation. The mother is preparing her daughter's tiffin box, and the daughter refuses to eat. The representation of women only as mothers or wives lends support to Amruthraj's (2012) findings about the concept of sexism.

4.2. Invisibility of women

Among the 61 people in the book, 11 are female, and among the 27 pictures of men and women, only 4 are of women in the old *EfT* textbook. There was a total of 16 women and 42 men, 7 pictures of female characters, and 18 pictures of male characters in the New *EfT* textbook. There were six female characters in Western literature, whereas there were 18 male characters. This highly disproportionate ratio clearly indicates the invisibility of women.

4.3. Women as insignificant

Here the most important female personality is Sri Lankan President Srimavo Bandarnaike, who appears in a news title with her death news. The death of the world's first female premier was probably more important than any of her achievements as a news report. The textbook talks about two female astronauts and two female space walkers. The only literature by a female writer was Marjorie Kinn Rowling. She was not chosen because she was prominent of her time, but rather because her short story, *A Mother in Manville*, was very popular in HSC level, the way *Gift of the Magi* was.

4.4. Identity negligence

The historical contribution of Nelson Mandela to impede race discrimination is described in unit 1, lesson 1. In this lesson, three more names appeared. They are F.W. de Klerk, the white African leader who freed Mandela from prison, and Nadine Gordimer, the South African writer and Nobel Laureate for Literature, who made a remark on Mandela and President P.W. Botha, whom Mandela met in prison. These three men are found with full names and identification, but when it came to the name of Winnie, it appeared as 'his wife Winnie' (p. 11). It is not clear, whether she is Winnie Mandela or if Winnie is her nickname. It seems that mentioning 'his wife' or Mandela's wife is enough to establish her identity. Winnie's individual identity is neglected here. Winnie's contribution as a devoted wife was evident from the comment "walking away from the Victor Verster prison hand-in-hand with his wife Winnie" (p. 11). It also suggests that for a successful man or a struggling man, a dedicated wife is very important. All of these are only implied, but not directly stated. Thus, this new *EfT* textbook, like the old *EfT* textbook, posits women as wives rather than identity-owning individual human beings.

4.5. Lack of equal participation

The title of unit 1 is 'People or Institutions Making History', where two leaders are described: Nelson Mandela, the South African President and apartheid fighter, and Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, the strongest leader for whom we achieved independence. Lesson 3 deals with two women, Valentina Tereshkova and Kalpana Chawla, for their extraordinary achievements in space. These names could have been elaborated in unit 13, 'Greatest Scientific Achievement', where we find the names of Neil Armstrong and Buzz Aldrin. In addition, in unit 1 lesson 3, it could have been possible to select a reading passage based on women leaders contributing to their countries, such as Srimavo Bandarnaike,¹ the world's first non-hereditary female head of state or government in modern history, and the elected Prime Minister of Sri Lanka in 1960 or Indira Gandhi,² the first and, to date, the only female Prime Minister of India. Indira Gandhi was the daughter of Jawaharlal Nehru, the first prime minister of India. For example, in the lesson 'Things We Enjoy Doing', people from different countries are found enjoying themselves in three illustrations in the old book. Women are walking or eating, but men attempt adventurous activities like snowboarding or surfing only. This is a way of excluding women from equal participation.

4.6. Contrasting description of women

Alternatively, the six European and English women also prove the very nature of womanhood. Hence, women are more appreciated in household activities in the new textbook as well. Elizabeth, the dignified British woman in search of a husband in the new book, and Mrs. Cynthia Fraser, Robert's mother leading a perfect life in the old book, are also posited in domestic affairs, but they are given strength, status, and freedom. However, both are gracefully delineated, a quality for target culture women but not for Asian women.

In 'Cruelties of Conflict', the description of black American civil rights activist Maya Angelou included her rape case as well. Dickinson's death poems indicate that she may have suffered some sort of abuse. Such an incident could have been with any other English or American person, but it is included only in the case of a black person. It was incorporated to make her appear pitiful and her reason to become an activist.

4.7. Women in sports

The textbooks displayed favorite sports for men in Japan but not any sports for women. The old book neglected Asian female players in the old book. Venus Williams was the only American female tennis player found among eight English and Asian players. It seems as if there are rarely any Asian female players. Names such as Saniya Mirza (India), Naomi Osaka (Japan), tennis

players, and so on could have been suitable examples to be included in *EFT* textbooks.

4.8. Discrimination in profession

The professions allocated for women in the old book are deceased president, office workers, astronauts, and receptionists, whereas men are kings, emperors, leaders, sports icons, doctors, chefs, astronauts, teachers, and wage-earners. In the new book, women are astronauts, actresses, writers, poets, teachers, geographers, film directors, songwriters, playwrights, athletes, swimmers, mountaineers, football players, aerobics and yoga instructors, whereas men are presidents, leaders, professors, vice chancellors, philosophers, journalists, editors, poets, writers, police officers, actors, soldiers, swimmers, managers, office workers, farmers, wage-earners, and blacksmiths. The new book gives women more space in sports. The new book presents women as self-independent and allows them to come out of gender role conformity. The textbooks represent white-collar jobs more prominently than blue-collar jobs.

The books also emphasize the importance of education. As these books are taught in colleges in rural Bangladesh, this emphasis may motivate unprivileged learners towards education. However, these sections do not interpret how students can choose their career considering their interests or hidden talents.

Thus, in all cases, the number of male figures was much higher than the number of female figures, which represents a higher order of inequality. It can be said that the intention of the book was to project male personalities only.

In Bangladesh, white-collar jobholders are successful and powerful. The textbooks show a similar picture. When a textbook glorifies predictable professions only, it may allow the students to assume that they cannot be successful unless they build up their career in those prescribed professions. The book should highlight some jobs for women as entrepreneurs, freelancing, and so on.

4.9. Class distinction

The new book vividly portrays stark social distinctions. It delineates a meticulously arranged classroom setting with well-dressed students engrossed in their studies, equipped with modern amenities like projectors and computers. A clean road with a marked zebra crossing, featuring orderly traffic, suggests an affluent environment. The list of fast-food items such as pizza, hot dogs, burgers, French fries, pastries, rolls, drumsticks, kabab, and chicken noodles further emphasizes a lifestyle associated with prosperity. The

depiction extends to a well-off university canteen, a neatly organized gym furnished with heavy equipment, and individuals, both adults and children, enjoying shopping. In stark contrast, the narrative introduces the harsh realities faced by street children engaged in rubbish collection, enduring nights on cold roads, undertaking strenuous manual labor, and grappling with persistent hunger and serious illnesses. It also highlights the plight of those who lose eyes while working in hazardous conditions, individuals living in tunnels, and half-naked women engaged in cooking.

The old book depicts some class differences, such as a nuclear family having a meal using a dining table chair, people using a telephone, computer, and newspaper, a well-equipped house, a well-equipped kitchen, women working in offices, people doing exercise, visiting places, and a multistory apartment. A contrasting picture also shows an open manhole on the road, below-standard education, poor infrastructure in educational institutions, politics and violence in educational institutions, people living in slums, street children, and children doing manual work. Such unequal class representation proves that *EfT* sustains some stereotyping and misrepresentations.

4.10. Unreasonable selection of cultural content

Noble Prize-winning poet Rabindranath Tagore is included as an Asian to heighten the status of Asia. However, in unit 6, 'An Eastern University', he states that European institutions are the best places for education. To learn from them, we should knock on the doors of France and Germany. It says, "Educational institutions in our country are India's alms bowl of knowledge; they lower our intellectual self-respect; they encourage us to make a foolish display of decorations composed of borrowed feathers" (p. 150).

While we accept this as a reality, there is no merit in informing the 11-12 graders in such a derogatory way. This can be a short story on the syllabus at universities. More importantly, this should be a concern of the University Grade Commission (UGC) to establish rules to improve the quality of education in Indian universities. Such an unreasonable selection of cultural content may make the readers of this book feel belittled and deprived. They may also think that associating with Western culture is the only way to improve their status in the world.

4.11. Cultural disparity

Evidence from the ELT textbooks displays some cultural disparity as well. Two African practices are mentioned; one is the traditional practice of polygamy, and the second is that relatives in Kenyan families stay with them to look for jobs. If polygamy was a practice in ancient Kenya, free sex, living together, gay sex, and so on are also common practices in modern Western countries.

However, such pejorative information about Western culture is never included in *EfT* textbooks.

The textbooks showed the favorite sports, pastimes, food and food habits, music, etiquette, festivals, citizenship, education, and personalities of Western countries courteously and with necessary explanation. In the case of Asian culture, it demonstrated family, pass time, sports, dress, food, etiquette, and tradition, but festivals were rarely depicted. The descriptions of African culture are very limited and superficially presented. Usually in Asian or African countries, if there is an elder in the family or guests arrive, the hostess serves the food to everyone, and then she eats. However, the sentence construction in the new book states “finally, women” (p. 109), which seems to admit women are forbidden to eat first. The textbook mentioned nothing about African food, festivals, sports, or leisure activities, but it was essential to inform learners that women have to eat after everybody has eaten.

The old book mostly presented women as wives and mothers rather than human beings. The old book did not only exclude women from participation; it also misrepresented women. It presented the work of women as humdrum as well as tedious. However, this was not the case while describing an English woman. On the contrary, the new textbook, though it paid more attention to women participation, was not thoughtful enough. That is, it did not equally present men and women. When the book described the revered leaders of Asian and African countries, it did not portray a woman leader. Still, appreciating women’s participation in sports is undoubtedly a token gesture.

4.12. Unequal representation of target culture

There were 18 countries from Asia and 8 countries from Africa mentioned in the old textbook. Whereas, in the new textbook, America is mentioned 51 times, England 38 times, Europe 26 times, Asia 24 times, and Africa 10 times. Mentioning the names of the USA or UK several times does not mean showing respect to them. The USA and UK are successful because of their education systems, medical treatment, human rights, law and enforcement, research, dedication, and less corruption. Learning such skills from English culture to be a global citizen would really uphold their importance.

The textbooks predominantly include names of cities, countries, famous tourists’ spots, buildings, and renowned personalities, like many foreign EFL textbooks (cf. Bose & Gao, 2022; Kusumaningrum et al., 2023; Saemee & Nomnian, 2021). These are tangible examples of foreign cultures beneficial for cultural knowledge and vocabulary learning. Many of the names of places and people are simply mentioned for information without arousing any motivation or triggering critical thinking. The old textbook showed a large fraction of target culture content more effectively than the new book. Practices and

perspectives, on the other hand, are implicit cultural representations of life and living, but they are effective language learning material. They determine the appropriate use of polished language and reinforce learners' tolerance, sociocultural awareness, and perspectives on global citizenship (Saemee & Nomnian, 2021). Although foreign practices are observed as one of the most crucial cultural aspects of English teaching textbooks, they are infrequently included in ELT textbooks (Davidson & Liu's, 2020; Raigón-Rodríguez, 2018). Similar is the case of *EfT* series. The old textbook provided more practice as it was a voluminous one. However, there was less than 50% in comparison to foreign products. Again, simply listing a number of norms, foods, and festivals would be interesting but may not be very effective for language competence. Arslan (2020) mentioned that language learners are not travelers, so simply providing information about customs, food, clothing, and institutions of another culture is not enough to increase cultural awareness. Learners need to be an active participant in a language learning process that truly interweaves culture.

4.13. Inclusion of etiquette

In unit 7, 'Lifestyle', two lessons on 'Basic Table Etiquette' and 'Etiquette Netiquette' are tremendous additions to the new book. Many teens lack table manners and respect for elders in Bangladesh. Either their families do not guide them or, even after guidance, they are still reluctant. The lesson on 'Etiquette Netiquette' also mentions basic manners to live in a modern city, such as living with neighbors, driving on roads, attitudes towards elders, comments and posts on *Facebook*, eating habits, and so on. They are very important for mutual respect and tolerance of differences in modern and global society.

5. Discussion

Based on the analyzed data, it can be acknowledged that the *EfT* textbooks contain two types of discrepancies: (1) disparate gender representations, and (2) biased cultural trait representations. In this section, key findings in relation to the cultural content of the textbooks will be summarized and compared to the existing reported literature.

5.1. Disparate gender representations

The *EfT* textbooks suffer from a serious gender bias. The representation of women in India, Myanmar, Japan, Afghanistan, and Kenya exhibits that women in Asia are more appreciated as wives doing domestic activities (e.g., India, p. 202, Afghanistan, p. 170, Myanmar, p. 4, Kenya, p. 7 (Japan is also implied)—Please also see 4.7 Women in sports)). The Taj Mahal, built for Emperor Shah

Jahan's wife, Mumtaz, also seems to support the idea. This is a static problem in South Asian countries (Bose & Gao, 2022; Islam & Asadullah, 2018). The notion of excluding women from equal participation and neglecting them are also examples of gender discrimination. The negligence towards the President's wife (see example of Winnie above) and the Sri Lankan President (see above) may support the claim that women are often underestimated and disrespected. The apparent degraded status of women in Asia has a sharp contrast with that of Western women. The western women are also represented in the *EfT* textbooks as mothers, wives, or would-be wives, but they are respected and have strong personalities.

The professions of Asian and African women in the *EfT* textbooks are mostly conventional and less esteemed. The female characters are found to be introverted, submissive, and passive in regards to personality traits (cf. Al Shalabi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2009), and are typically involved in domestic and in-door activities; they are portrayed as victimized, venerable, and subordinate. However, men are portrayed as powerful, authoritative, posited in higher professions, and active agents in family and society. Women are segregated in the text as well as in the illustrations.

This finding lends support to Kabir (2015), who commented that women are not appropriately projected in the *EfT* textbooks for Classes IX-X published by the NCTB (2012). Likewise, Islam & Asadullah (2018, p. 17) found a high degree of gender stereotypes in the form of "exclusion" and "the quality of representation" in all the textbooks in secondary schools (grade 9) in Malaysia, Indonesia, Pakistan, and Bangladesh. Our findings also support Suchana (2020), who revealed linguistic sexism, masculine dominance, and women enslavement in the *EfT* textbook of Class V. In much the same way, Asadullah et al. (2018) admitted that the pro-male bias pervaded all Bangladeshi school textbooks, regardless of whether they followed a secular or religious curriculum. Although the Bangladeshi government has taken steps to promote gender equality under the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of gender equality and empowering women, as well as implementing the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), women are still represented as a marginalized class, as evident in these ELT textbooks.

5.2. Biased cultural traits representations

The *EfT* series are essential textbooks used mandatorily in Bangladeshi public primary and secondary schools for English education. The main objective of learning English as one of the compulsory school subjects is to equip students with the ability to use the language for oral and written communication in various situations. As intercultural communicative competence has become a

prominent talent in this century, integrating culturally diverse content into *EFL* textbooks is a must in order to practice tolerance and raise cultural awareness. However, research studies on the cultural content of ELT textbooks show that they are still based on British and American cultural traits (Isnaini, et al., 2019; Kusumaningrum et al., 2023; Saemee & Nomnian, 2021; Zhang & Chang, 2022).

The unreasonable frequencies of western places, the accumulations of different western festivals without any explanations, the exclusion of Asian and African cultural traits just to highlight British and American culture, and including devaluing information about Asians and Africans are clear instances of cultural discrimination. Such a mindset will be incapable of producing global citizens. Learners can easily be led to misunderstandings and confusion, as they are probably unable to judge the content. Such contents can make learners believe that associating with British and American cultures is the solution to all of their crises.

Former British-colonized countries³ usually produce ELT textbooks with the dominance of target language cultural representations. Nevertheless, the present demand for ELT textbooks is to attain English language proficiency. This is not synonymous with learning Americanism or Westernism. Including target cultural contents is necessary for English language learners, but they should be presented only in such a way as to help them (1) acquire suitable input of intercultural competence, and (2) achieve the ability to express themselves in a proper way in English. As Kramsch (2013) argued, the teaching of culture will always remain a complex issue as, on the one hand, it has to follow modern objectives to identify and explain people and events and, on the other hand, it has to incorporate the post-modern subjectivities and living legends of globalized world. Thus, the job of a language teacher will be more complicated.

6. Conclusion

Our findings suggest that, although the inclusion of cultural elements in textbooks can impart knowledge to students, they still appear to lack, to a greater extent, the required skills and attitudes necessary for ICC development. The textbooks, though locally produced, highlight a strong inclination towards the cultures of the USA and UK, like other international ELT textbooks, which, according to Alptekin (2002), should no longer be a tradition in English language learning.

As for the communicative approach, culture functions as a complementary aid to achieving effective communication. English, being the international language, or *Lingua Franca*, should not solely represent Western culture. Thus, English language learners do need to be acquainted with intercultural communication skills to dynamically participate in global cross-cultural

communication. Otherwise, EFL/EIL learners will have “a one-track mind” (Arslan, 2020, p. 152).

Our first research question investigated cultural discrimination in the locally produced ELT textbooks at HSC level in Bangladesh. The analyzed data suggests that there are two prevalent types of discrimination; one is (1) gender disparity, which shows negligence towards women in every sphere and posits women mostly in conventional domestic affairs. However, when delineating a British woman, she was given more freedom and strength, as shown in the old textbook. In the new book, though there was discrimination, women were also appreciated in sports. The second discrimination is (2) the dominance of British and American cultural traits in the textbooks. Mentioning the names of countries, cities, and people of Western countries several times does not show any respect towards them; rather, something important about their cultural practices would enhance the intercultural aspects of our learners’ competence.

The second research question of this study dealt with the extent of the idea of cultural diversity addressed in HSC textbooks in Bangladesh. The two textbooks apparently presented cultural diversity by addressing four cultural categories: (1) product, (2) person, (3) practice, and (4) perspective of Western as well as Asian and African countries. However, findings show that cultural diversity is sometimes used to highlight the target language culture. In this connection, Canale (2016) has presented two reasons: One is (1) to lessen the burden of information of foreign culture, and another is (2) to suppress the voices conflicting with hegemonic ideologies. Because it was frequently the Western culture depicted in *Eft* Books at the expense of Asian and African cultures, cultural relativism was extremely neglected (cf. Galante, 2015).

In Bangladesh, textbook contents are often manipulated to serve the political purposes and the ideologies of the governments (Islam & Asadullah, 2018). The textbook development committee focuses mostly on creating a national identity through textbooks. In such circumstances, gender disparity in the curriculum and the learning materials remains unnoticed. Islam and Asadullah (2018) state that the national textbook board authority most probably thinks that gender representations in texts should reflect the prevalent system of the country. This shows that removing stereotypes from school textbooks and classroom activities might not be sufficient to achieve the SDGs of gender equality by 2030. A major obstacle still lies in getting policymakers to think differently. Therefore, Asadullah et al. (2018) proposed that, rather than relying on political language, the aim of promoting gender-equitable textbooks and learning materials should be substantiated by data. The nation’s textbook board chairs and directors apparently think that gender representations in school texts should reflect the status quo of the society. This, too, shows that merely shifting the emphasis in policy papers to remove stereotypes from

school textbooks and classroom activities might not be sufficient to achieve the SDGs of gender equality by 2030. Yet again, a major obstacle still lies in getting policymakers to think differently.

Nevertheless, gender-insensitive curricula and/or learning materials may especially suppress women's voices although the crucial role of education should be to deal with the prevailing causes of gender discrimination in society. This is an urgent concern because our country has agreed to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and joined the worldwide community to ensure gender equality in education. Thus, our country is expected to follow the indicative strategy recommended in Education 2030 Target 4.5 of SDG 4: "The Incheon Declaration commits to non-discriminatory education that recognizes the importance of gender equality and women's empowerment for sustainable development" (Mundial & UNICEF, 2016).

Gender equitable textbooks will presumably change the conceptual position of the learner and will make them aware of women's rights, which a unit in *Eft* textbooks on 'woman rights' will not change. Female learners, in particular, will have a say against such marginalization. They should also be able to confront some of the social crimes—like bullying, teasing, or raping. Needless to say, children learn about cultural practice, manners, etiquettes, as well as the perspectives of life, from textbooks that forms their mindsets (Suchana, 2020). Thus, the standpoint of the materials developer to design (1) the power and potentials of both males and females and (2) equal visibility of men and women can be the two criteria for preparing gender-balanced textbooks.

For equal representation of foreign cultural aspects, the ICC model highlighting knowledge, skills, and attitudes can be effective. Intercultural competence cannot be feasible through knowing solely about festivals, food culture, or some other customs of any given culture, nor will mentioning the name of America or American cities increase respect for them. Rather, including lessons on foreign practices, such as Etiquette and Netiquette, may help learners grow as global citizens and can likely equip them to achieve effective intercultural communication.

It should be noted that Jahan (2012) advised the local experts to assume authorial ownership of textbooks, as English is used to express imperialism in global ELT materials. Suchana (2020) stated that gender discrimination in local ELT materials could be unintentional. It is, therefore, imperative for ELT textbook writers, publishers, other stakeholders, and NCTB to allot a suitable number of national and international cultural representations to enable learners to recognize various cultural practices in multicultural contexts. Moreover, a participatory approach that ensures a critical review of curriculum and *Eft* textbooks on gender issues is also obligatory.

The key implication of this research refers to some changes in the existing *EFT* textbooks in terms of the nature of content, task, and activity patterns, as well as the selection of illustrations to trigger critical thinking on multicultural learning through cultural practices. The study highlights the important role played by illustrations as well as cultural representations in language learning textbooks. The implication of this study is to prepare instructional materials and activities that contain suitable discourse samples with authentic illustrations to enhance cultural learning. The illustrations ought to be comprehensible to reinforce linguistic competence; they need to be tuned properly with extracts from literature to pave the way for critical thinking. Another important implication of this study refers to the nature of the content of the textbooks. It is imperative to stop projecting stereotyped concepts of Asian social life, such as women doing household chores and raising babies only. The view of the world from a woman's perspective, a non-native's perspective, etc. should be included. Moreover, an abridged, well-sized extract from a multicultural context in Standard English highlighting specific cultural practices should be included.

All in all, the existing shortcomings of *English for Today* textbooks are unlikely to go away soon. Hence, it should be the responsibility of the teachers in high schools to provide some support by using multimedia and online videos to increase the depth of students' cultural knowledge and use of the English language, as the present government has provided multimedia, laptops, and internet facilities in the schools for rural areas as well.

Notes

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sirimav_Bandaranaike
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Indira_Gandhi
3. For more on colonization and educational equity, see Chaka (2024), Mapuya (2024), Salmani Nodoushan (2024), and Xu and Fang (2024).

Authors' Statement

Massrura Mostafa wrote the entire first draft of the paper. Rubaiyat Jahan edited and revised the first draft of the paper and brought it to the present shape.

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References

- Al Shalabi, M. F., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009). Personality theory and TESOL. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 3(1), 14-22.
- Alptekin C. (2002). Towards intercultural communicative competence in ELT. *ELT Journal*, 56, 57-64. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/56.1.57>
- Amruthraj, R. M. (2012). Gender discrimination in the primary school English language textbooks in Tamil Nadu. *The Primary Teacher*, 37(1&2), 77-101.
- Apple, M. W., & Christian-Smith, L. K. (2017). The politics of the textbook. In M. Apple & L. K. Christian-Smith (Eds.), *The politics of the textbook* (pp. 1-21). Routledge.
- Arslan, S. (2020). Culture in textbooks and curricula. In S. Çelik & E. Solak (Eds.), *World Englishes and culture in English as a foreign language (EFL) education* (pp. 143-158). Vize Yayıncılık.
- Asadullah, M. N., Islam, K. M. M., & Wahhaj, Z. (2018). Gender bias in Bangladeshi school textbooks: Not just a matter of politics or growing influence of Islamists. *The Review of Faith & International Affairs*, 16(2), 84-89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15570274.2018.1469821>
- Bose, P., & Gao, X. (2022). Cultural representations in Indian English language teaching textbooks. *SAGE Open*, 12, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221082102>
- Canale, G. (2016). (Re)Searching culture in foreign language textbooks, or the politics of hide and seek. *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 29, 225-243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2016.1144764>

- Canale, G. (2021). The language textbook: Representation, interaction & learning: Conclusions. *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 34(2), 199-206. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2020.1797081>
- Chaka, C. (2024). Multilingualism, translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice, and activism: A tenuous nexus and misrepresentations? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 7-28.
- Chang, S.-C. (2004). Integrating cultural education into FL class for intercultural communication. *Soochow Journal of Foreign Languages and Cultures*, 19, 203-221.
- Cortazzi, M., & Jin, L. (1999). Cultural mirrors: Materials and methods in the EFL classroom. In E. Hinkel (Ed.), *Culture in second language teaching* (pp. 196-219). Cambridge University Press.
- Davidson, R., & Liu, Y. (2020). Reaching the world outside: Cultural representation and perceptions of global citizenship in Japanese elementary school English textbooks. *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 33(1), 32-49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2018.1560460>
- Galante, A. (2015). Intercultural communicative competence in English language teaching: Towards validation of student identity. *Brazilian English Language Teaching Journal*, 6(1), 29-39. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15448/2178-3640.2015.1.20188>
- Graves, K. (2021). Materials in the language classroom. In H. Mohebbi & C. Coombe (Eds.), *Research questions in language education and applied linguistics*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79143-8_22
- Gurney, L., & Díaz, A. (2020). Coloniality, neoliberalism and the language textbook: Unravelling the symbiosis in Spanish as a foreign language. *Language, Culture and Society*, 2(2), 149-173. <https://doi.org/10.1075/lcs.20003.gur>
- Işık, A. (2018). ELT materials evaluation: A system and criteria. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 8(7), 797-812. <https://doi.org/10.17507/tpls.0807.11>
- Islam, K. M. M., & Asadullah, M. N. (2018). Gender stereotypes and education: A comparative content analysis of Malaysian, Indonesian, Pakistani and Bangladeshi school textbooks. *PLoS one*, 13(1), e0190807. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0190807>

- Isnaini, F., Setyono, B., Ariyanto, S. (2019). A visual semiotic analysis of multicultural values in an Indonesian English textbook. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 8(3), 536-544. <https://doi.org/17509/ijal.v8i315253>
- Jahan, A. (2012). Residual cultural imperialism in primary textbooks in Bangladesh: A critique of the *English for Today* textbooks. *East West University Journal*, 3, 73-94.
- Kabir, M. M. N. (2015). Representation of women in Bangladeshi ELT materials. *The Dhaka University Journal of Linguistics*, 5-6(9-12), 127-146.
- Karakuş, E. (2021). A systematic review of the representation of cultural elements in English as a Foreign Language textbooks. *Language Teaching and Educational Research*, 4(1), 13-29.
- Kim, S. Y., & Paek, J. (2015). An analysis of culture-related content in English textbooks. *Linguistic Research*, 32(Special Edition), 83-104. <https://doi.org/10.17250/khisli.32.201507.005>
- Kramersch, C. (1991). Culture in language learning: A view from the United States. In K. de Bot, R. B. Ginsberg & C. Kramersch (Eds.), *Foreign language research in cross-cultural perspective* (pp. 217-240). John Benjamins.
- Kramersch, C. (2011). The symbolic dimensions of the intercultural. *Language Teaching*, 44(3), 354-367.
- Kramersch, C. (2013). Culture in foreign language teaching. *Iranian journal of language teaching research*, 1(1), 57-78.
- Kusumaningrum, A., Suparno, S., & Sumardi, S. (2023). The cultural representation in secondary EFL textbooks: A critical content analysis and teachers' perceptions. *Journal of Innovation in Educational and Cultural Research*, 4(3), 399-409. <https://doi.org/10.46843/jiecr.v4i3.729>
- Mapuya, M. (2024). Exploring the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies: Promoting social justice in accounting education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 131-155.
- Moran, P. (2001). *Teaching culture: Perspectives in practice*. Heinle & Heinle.

- Mundial, G. B., & UNICEF. (2016). Education 2030: Incheon declaration and framework for action: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000245656>
- National Curriculum & Textbook Board. (2012). *National Curriculum, Classes XI-XII*.
- Ndlangamandla, S. C. (2024). The coloniality of English proficiency and EMI: Decolonization, language equity, and epistemic (in)justice. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 105-130.
- Nurjanah, I., & Umaemah, A. (2019). An analysis of cultural content in the textbook "*Pathway to English*" for second grade in senior high school. *ELT-Echo*, 4(1), 83-92. <https://doi.org/10.24235/eltecho.v4i1.4536>
- Raigón-Rodríguez, A. (2018). Analysing cultural aspects in EFL textbooks: A skill-based analysis. *Journal of English Studies*, 16, 281-300. <https://doi.org/10.18172/jes.3478>.
- Risager, K. (2023). Analysing culture in language learning materials. *Language Teaching*, 56(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444822000143>
- Saemee, K., & Nomnian, S. (2021). Cultural representations in ELT textbooks used in a multicultural school. *rEFlections*, 28(1), 107-120. Retrieved from: <https://repository.li.mahidol.ac.th/handle/123456789/75872>.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2024). Language colonization or lingua franca? Demystifying the status quo of Persian. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 63-90.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Daftarifard, P. (2011). Globalized classroom, emancipatory competence, and critical pedagogy: A paradigm shift. In R. V. Nata (Ed.), *Progress in education* (pp. 147-162). Nova Science Publishers, Inc.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Pashapour, A. (2016). Critical pedagogy, rituals of distinction, and true professionalism. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 13(1), 29-43.
- Suchana, A. A. (2020). Investigating gender equity in a primary level English language textbook in Bangladesh. In S. Sultana, M. M. Roshid, M. Z. Haider, M. M. N. Kabir & M. H. Khan (Eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of English Language Education in Bangladesh* (pp. 298-311). Routledge.

- Weninger, C., & Kiss, T. (2013). Culture in English as a foreign language (EFL) textbooks: A semiotic approach. *TESOL Quarterly*, 47(4), 694-716. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.87>
- Xu, Y., & Fang, F. (2024). Promoting educational equity: The implementation of translanguaging pedagogy in English language education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 53-80.
- Yuen, K. (2011). The representation of foreign cultures in English textbooks. *ELT Journal*, 65(4), 458-466. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccq089>.
- Zhang, H., Li, X., & Chang, W. (2022). Representation of cultures in national English textbooks in China: A synchronic content analysis. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2022.2099406>